

A Study of Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycine with Some Metal Ions : Part XI. Cu (II) Chelates Containing Both Biguanidine and N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycines

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Biguanidines¹ and N-benzenesulphonyl glycines^{2,3} are well known bidentate chelating agents. The present communication consists of Cu(II) chelates containing both types of ligands. For the preparation of such compounds, the ligands employed are (a) biguanidine (BigH), (b) phenylbiguanidine (PhbigH), (c) N-benzenesulphonyl glycine (R_bH_2), (d) N-benzenesulphonyl (*dl*) α -alanine ($R^{\alpha}_bH_2$), (e) N-*p* toluenesulphonyl glycine (R_tH_2), (f) N-*p* toluenesulphonyl (*dl*) α -alanine ($R^{\alpha}_tH_2$), (g) N-benzenesulphonyl β -alanine ($R^{\beta}_bH_2$).

EXPERIMENTAL

All the ligands were prepared in the laboratory following the methods stated in the literature.

General method for the preparation of Cu(II) chelates : A clear aqueous solution of phenylbiguanidine hydrochloride (PhbigH, HCl) or biguanidine sulphate (BigH, H_2SO_4) was treated with sodium acetate in order to adjust pH between 3.4–3.5. This solution was then added to an equimolecular solution of $Cu(RH_2)$ in water at room temperature containing excess of RH_2 . If necessary, pH of the resulting mixture was readjusted to 3.4–3.5 with sodium acetate. On stirring a violet compound separated, filtered, washed with water and finally with ethanol and air dried. Molecular composition corresponded to $Cu(Phbig)(RH)$ or $Cu(Big)(RH)$. With ligand $R^{\beta}_bH_2$, however, such could not be isolated but a brick-red compound separated at pH 9 which corresponded to $Cu(PhbigH)_2(R^{\beta}_bH)_2$.

A compound was also prepared by treating the aqueous solution of $Cu(PhbigH)_2Cl_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ with a solution of $Na_2Cu(R_b)_2$ in equimolecular quantities, immediate separation of a blue compound having the composition $Cu(Phbig)(R_bH) \cdot \frac{1}{2}H_2O$ took place. On heating at 110° it lost its water molecule and colour changed to violet. The dehydrated product had the same colour and composition as that obtained by the general method already stated. Analytical data are shown in Table-I.

All the compounds are insoluble in water and complexes of the series $Cu(Phbig)(RH)$ are sparingly soluble in ethanol whereas those of the series $Cu(Big)(RH)$ are practically insoluble.

1. P. Ray, *Chem. Reviews*, 1961, **61**, 313.
2. N. N. Ghosh and M. N. Majumdar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 945; 1967, **44**, 115 and 559.
3. N. N. Ghosh and A. Bhattacharyya, *Science and Culture*, 1969, **35**, 270.

TABLE I

Composition, analyses and magnetic data of the compounds

Serial No.*	Composition of the compounds	% Copper		% Nitrogen		μ_{eff} in B.M.	Temp. in °K
		Found	Required	Found	Required		
1.	Cu(Big) (R _b H)	16.90	16.82	21.90	22.25	1.83	303
2.	Cu(Big) (R ^α _b H)	16.12	16.22	21.30	21.46	1.85	303
3.	Cu(Big) (R _t H)	15.96	16.22	21.70	21.46	1.89	303
4.	Cu(Big) (R ^α _t H)	15.81	15.66	21.30	20.71	1.92	302
5.	Cu(Phbig) (R _b H)	13.70	14.01	18.40	18.52	1.89	302
6.	Cu(Phbig) (R ^α _b H)	13.33	13.58	17.30	17.97	1.83	303
7.	Cu(Phbig) (R _t H)	13.42	13.58	17.50	17.97	1.87	303
8.	Cu(Phbig) (R ^α _t H)	12.98	13.19	16.90	17.45	1.80	302
9.	Cu(Phbig) (R _b H); $\frac{1}{2}$ H ₂ O	13.62	13.73	18.01	18.17	1.84	302
10.	Cu(Phbig) (R _b H)	14.13	14.01	18.03	18.52	1.88	302
11.	Cu(PhbigH) ₂ (R ^β _b H) ₂	7.29	7.25	18.60	19.20	1.89	302

* Nos 9 and 10 were obtained by metathesis.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of all Cu(II) chelates were made at room temperature and data obtained after diamagnetic corrections are stated in Table-I. Electronic spectra in ethanolic solution of sparingly soluble complexes were measured at room temperature and data are included in Table II.

TABLE II

Electronic spectra of some of the compounds

Compounds	$\lambda_{max}^{ethanol}$ in $m\mu$	$\log \epsilon$	Compounds	$\lambda_{max}^{ethanol}$ in $m\mu$	$\log \epsilon$
Cu(Phbig) (R _b H)	580	1.79	Cu(Phbig) (H ^α _t H)	570	1.68
	243	4.23		244	4.19
Cu(Phbig) (R ^α _b H)	580	1.75	*Cu(Phbig) (R _b H); $\frac{1}{2}$ H ₂ O	580	1.78
	242	4.19		243	4.20
Cu(Phbig) (R _t H)	570	1.70	*Cu(Phbig) (R _b H)	580	1.78
	244	4.20		243	4.20

* These compounds were prepared by metathesis.

Results on thermogravimetry and I.R. spectra in KBr matrix, of both the compounds having the composition Cu(Phbig)(R_bH) obtained by the general method as well as by metathesis were found to be identical.

DISCUSSION

The observed magnetic moment values for most Cu(II) compounds are 1.8 to 2.2 B.M.⁴ In the present cases also expected values are obtained as shown in Table-I. In a previous communication⁵ subnormal values for Cu(RH)₂ and normal values on salt

4. A. E. Martell and M. Calvin, *Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds*, Prentice-Hall, Inc., N. Y., 1952.

5. N. N. Ghosh and A. Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 1040

formation, have been reported. Therefore it appears safer to represent these complexes assuming monomeric, as $\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{R}^-)$ rather than $\text{Cu}(\text{Big})(\text{RH})$.

However, these complexes may also be dimeric when they are likely to be represented by $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}[\text{Cu}(\text{R})_2]^{2-}$ or $[\text{Cu}(\text{PhbigH})_2]^{2+}[\text{Cu}(\text{R})_2]^{2-}$. So a compound of this type, $[\text{Cu}(\text{PhbigH})_2]^{2+}[\text{Cu}(\text{R}_b\text{H})_2]^{2-}$ has been prepared by metathesis for a comparative study with the compound of the same composition obtained by the first method. Their magnetic moment values and electronic spectra in ethanolic solution are found to be similar. So one may assume that they are same compound. Further evidences for their identity are shown by their identical thermogravimetric curves and infra-red spectra. In conclusion, these compounds could not be regarded as mixed ligand chelates represented by $\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{R}_b^-)$, but to be assigned to its dimeric formula as $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}[\text{Cu}(\text{R}_b)_2]^{2-}$.

Our thanks are due to Dr. A. K. Sengupta of Kalyani University for thermogravimetry and the Director, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow for I.R. spectra. One of us (A.B.) is also thankful to U.G.C. for providing a research fellowship.

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Received July 27, 1970

